

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Waste is an integral part of human existence derived from the consumption of both food and resources which are invaluable for sustenance, these waste accumulate over time and has an adverse effect on the human health and the environmental condition, and therefore creates an urgent need for effective management. These wastes include leftover waste from the public, industries, offices, schools, streets, etc. Thus, the increase in population in our society has resulted in a concurrent increase in waste disposal leading to serious socio-economic and cultural issues. Almost all the streets, cities, roads in our country Nigeria, are froth with spilled trash while garbage is often littered around waste bins. The area around these improperly maintained waste bins breed disease spreading insects like mosquitoes, flies, bees and cockroaches, as well as ants and rodents etc., which are harmful to man. These improperly managed waste bins pollute the air, and the environment around the dustbin. This is responsible for the current increase in air pollution levels, greenhouse gas emission and general rise in waste standards. Air pollution due to waste bin or littered garbage also increase the risk of bacterial, fungi, viral infections and diseases which can be life threatening to human beings resulting in effects that are very unsafe for both humans and animals.

Everyone wants clean and beautiful things including a clean environment. Waste bins provided by the environmental management sector of the government and society, are used for moot decoration on roads that are not properly maintained, not attractive and very dirty. Poor provision of waste management facilities by the government in our society, also contributes to the environmental waste problem in our environment. This indicates that infective waste disposal maybe on increase due to the unsafe, messy and grossly inefficient

existing methods of waste disposal, in which the wastebin lid has to be manually opened by the user with his bare hands, further exposing the individual to bacterial and microbial contaminations.

Within the federal university Otuoke students also tend to litter the school premises. This is also caused by the fact that waste bins are few, far from reach, unattractive, conventional, dirty and poorly maintained. This is likely as a result of the ineffective waste disposal methods available, as well as the loose approach of the university community to the disposal of garbage or trash into the right places ergo garbage bins. This has created the need for research into the design and implementation of smart, efficient and economical waste bins. This " smart" waste bin features a lid that opens automatically as soon as the user approaches it to throw in trash, monitors the bin level, and once the bin is filled, an SMS alert is sent to the school department of works for proper disposal. The waste bins also segregates the waste into different compartments (metallic and non-metallic) with a sliding tray beneath that opens the disposal unit of the filled waste disposal bin bag by the management, for proper disposal and recycling. This waste disposal system also comprises a contact free hand washer for use after waste disposal, to reduce spread of disease through contact between the hand and trash disposal, thereby reducing the risk of transmission of COVID-19 and other infectious diseases. This contactless waste bin will result in a direct reduction of disease transmission and infection within the institution.

1.1 Problem of the Statement

Prevention or curbing the spread of contagious diseases, which are transmitted via contact between the infected and non-infected persons, has been the major health challenge making the spread and control of the COVID-19 pandemic difficult and complicated. It is already a well-known fact that garbage spillage results in unhealthy environments, which is very unsafe for

man and poses a health threat because it harbors disease-causing insects or organisms. Man must be prepared in this era for a more dangerous outbreak than COVID-19, although the current exponential population growth and population density increase of the world has made the control of contagious disease and waste management very difficult. The real time monitoring smart waste bin and contact free hand washing system developed in this research intends to reduce this problem to the barest minimum, via its contact-less approach which will be of immense help in achieving a sanitary environment with zero waste standards, and in return providing a solution to the spread and transmission of the COVID-19 virus.

1.2 Aim of the Research

The aim of this work is the development of real time monitoring smart waste bin with an integrated contact free hand washer.

1.3 Objectives of the Research

The specific objectives of the research are to:

- a) Design and locally fabricate a waste bin, with an SMS alert content monitoring system, and two separate waste disposal compartments;
- b) integrate an under-sliding locked disposal unit;
- c) fabricate and include a contact free hand washer to the waste bin; and,
- d) evaluate the developed waste bin and hand washing system to determine the efficiency of its performance.

1.3 Scope of study

The scope of this research is to develop a real time monitoring smart waste bin with an integrated contact free hand washer for efficient waste disposal, with the aim of reducing the spread of contagion in the environment, providing a conducive and clean environment. Also

to improve proper waste disposal and recycling in general offering a COVID-19 based solution system to the university and society at large.

1.4 Justification of the Research.

Waste segregation has become an important task as separating waste helps to avoid unnecessary work. Waste segregation not only helps in our domestic lifestyle but it is also useful for our environment to be safe. Waste is a necessary concern to look upon as the population increases. It is becoming important to understand the importance of waste management and keeping our surroundings clean. Also, the effect of waste on the environment can be controlled by managing waste. (Akshay and Nilima *et al.*, 2020)

Sandeep, (2017) created a system that monitors the garbage bins and informs the management about the level of garbage collected through a web page. The data in the web page is filtered and sent to the garbage collection vehicles. The system uses ultrasonic sensors placed over the bins to detect and measure the garbage level and compare it to the depth of the bin. The system is implemented using an Arduino-Uno processor and an LCD screen to display the bin status.

Akshatha, (2018) has proposed a garbage bin monitoring system for dry solids. This method implies that the dustbins interface with the Arduino, possessing weight sensors which collect information regarding the current status of refuse. All the data carried out are passed on to the app. The pressure sensor detects the level of garbage, whenever the garbage level reaches the threshold, the sensor notifies the Arduino-Uno. The data from Arduino is uploaded to the cloud storage. The push notification is then sent to the android application running in the registered android mobile device.

Navghanya, (2018) made an IOT based smart garbage and waste collection bin. In this system, the waste bins are connected to a microcontroller with a wireless IR system. The web page

carries information about the status of the garbage through WIFI. An IR sensor is used to give status about different levels of garbage in the bin. The weight sensor gets activated on crossing the threshold level. Their proposed work is to use a sensor-based system which is inexpensive rather than to use expensive smart bins. Also, they use 3 IR sensors to indicate each level in the dustbin and they have a wi-fi router to receive the instant status of the bin.

This research proposes to fill the gaps by the design of a real time monitoring waste bin for smart campus with the use of Arduino-Uno processor, stepper motor, sensors, and SMS module to implement a contact less waste bin system. This will monitor the level of garbage in the bin and notify the management authorities. A locked waste disposal unit accessible to the relevant waste management authorities separates the waste into two compartments with an integrated contactless hand washing machine. This is to provide a safer, contagion free environment, effective waste recycling and to reduce the spread of disease through contact. Thereby, creating an effective solution-based system for the control of the spread of diseases like COVID-19.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Concept of Waste

Most human activities generate waste (Brunner and Rechberger, 2014). Despite that, the production of wastes has remained a major source of concern since pre-historic periods (Chandler *et al.*, 1997). In recent times, the rate and quantity of waste generation has been on the increase. As the volume of wastes increase, so also does the variety of the waste (Vergara and Tchobanoglous, 2012). Unlike the pre-historic period where wastes were merely a source of nuisance that needed to be disposed, proper management was not a major issue as the population was small and a vast amount of land was available to the population at that time. In those days, the environment easily absorbed and transformed the volume of waste produced with minimal effect (Tchobanoglous *et al.*, 1993). A substantial increase in the volume of waste generation began in the sixteenth century when people began to move from rural areas to cities as a result of the industrial revolution (Wilson, 2007). This migration of people to cities led to population explosion that in turn led to a surge in the volume as well as an increase in the variety and composition of wastes generated in cities. It was then that materials such as metals and glass began to appear in large quantities in municipal waste streams (Williams, 2005). The unhealthy waste management practices resulted in several outbreaks of epidemics with high death tolls (Tchobanoglous *et al.*, 1993). Consequently, in the nineteenth century public officials began to dispose of waste in a controlled manner in order to safeguard public health (Tchobanoglous *et al.*, 1993). Most developed countries passed through a period when they were developing environmentally. Today, however, most of these countries have effectively addressed much of the health and environmental pollution issues associated with waste generation. An important question

in modern day waste management is – what exactly is a waste? Wastes can be defined as any product or material which is useless to the producer (Basu, 2009). A substance regarded as a waste to one individual, may be a resource to another. Therefore, a material can only be regarded as a waste when the owner labels it as such (Dijkema *et al*, 2000). Despite this subjective nature of wastes, it is important to describe clearly what constitutes wastes. This is because the classification of a material as a waste, forms the foundation for the regulations required to safeguard the populace and the different environments where the wastes are disposed or processed (Defra, 2009).

2.1.2 Smart Waste Bins

Man in his quest for good and sustainable environment, once adopted various methods of disposal, in the ancient era waste materials like piece of bones, wood, vegetable etc. were buried, burned, dumped into flowing rivers or oceans, etc., man adopted this disposal method till 200 AD, when wagons were used to collect waste material and dump them in an isolated distant site.

According to the report from Trash Cans Depots, (2021), the present-day closed trash cans derive their design idea from the first-ever garbage containers used in France. In 1883, Eugene Poubelle, an official in the French government, formed the Poubelle Law, which entails the use of closed trash cans. French citizens had to collect household waste in different containers based on their recycling capacity. For instance, rotting waste was disposed of in a separate trash receptacle, cloth and paper in one, and glass, oyster shells, and pottery in another. It was also stated in that report, that in the 1920s, an efficiency expert and industrial engineer by name Lillian Moller Gilbreth invented pedal bins; these are bins where the lid is opened by pressing the pedal attached to the bottom of the bin. During the 2010s, automated trash bins were introduced. An example of these type of trash bins is the sensor fitted type; these bins have an infrared detection mechanism fitted

to the trash can top. Batteries provide power for the sensors, instead of a foot pedal lifting the lid of the trash can, the sensor and the battery power helps open the lid. This prevents the user from touching the bins, in order to dispose of waste.

2.1.3 Hand Washing Machines

Importance of hand washing cannot be over-emphasized, especially in developing nations where eating with the hands is a common practice. Most people are always reluctant to wash their hands before meals; while for others, hand washing has become a culturally accepted norm. So, along the way, through technology and hygienic practices, people have become educated on the benefits of hand washing consequently resulting in an improvement in hand washing and general hygienic practices. Hand washing is the single most effective way to prevent the spread of infections (Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety, 2021). Unwashed or poorly washed hands are a very common way of spreading many diseases such as: cold, flu, ear infections, strep throat, diarrhea and other intestinal problems. The germs and viruses causing these are passed on by such routine things as handling food, touching door knobs, shaking hands and putting mouths or lips too close to a telephone receiver. And in our daily activities we practice one of these either in the offices, at home, in the market places, in the classroom and so on. Good hand washing practices have also been known to reduce the occurrence and spread of other diseases, notably pneumonia, trachoma, scabies, skin and eye infections and diarrhea-related diseases like cholera and dysentery, spread of COVID-19 virus.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the promotion of hand washing with soaps, alcohol based solutions, sanitizers, etc. is also a key strategy for controlling the spread of Avian Influenza (bird flu), severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in 2003, and COVID -19 virus in 2019-2020. The World Health Organization observed from their data that people generally gave

more attention to health habits and incorporated it into their daily lives; especially during and after the COVID era, consequently, the daily number of hand-washing increased (WHO, 2020).

Automatic hand washing machines were first developed in the 1950s, but were not produced for commercial use till the late 1980s when they first appeared (to the general public) at airport lavatories. Automatic hand washing machines are also called by other names including electronic, sensor, hands-free, “touch-less” or even infrared hand washing machines. Automatic hand washing machines have become a central theme in the American experience. They are now found in places, far removed from airports and other institutions, places like restaurants, hotels, casinos, malls, sports arenas as well as residential properties. Known for their assistive qualities, automatic hand washing machines are making their presence felt at living establishments and places where the elderly and or handicapped individuals call home.

2.2 Review of Related Studies.

The inappropriate disposal of garbage contributes to the spread of many diseases. In the bid to maintain good health and a clean environment, a smart water dispenser system and a smart waste disposal system became necessary as the individuals need to ensure healthy waste disposal, as well as wash their hands after disposing waste. This led to various research and designs. One of which include the Smart Waste Management by Rathod and others (Rathod *et al.*, 2019) where a waste management system was monitored for disposal through a web portal on the internet using a WiFi module.

One of the breakthroughs in the field of waste management was the Automated waste segregator with four compartments on waste differentiation into nylon, plastic, iron and the others (Alfred Ama, 2020), which had a device-user interface, sensor for waste determination, bin-full detection system and a feedback website.

Segregation and Optimal Distribution of the bins was modeled by (Saranya *et al.*, 2020), with a metal and non-metal segregator, using a NodeMCU to send the data status of the bin. The level of the bin is monitored in real time using an ultrasonic sensor, and a web-service IFTTT (If This Then That) a free cloud based service is used to send an alert email to the concerned authority.

A revised IOT based trash collection bin using Arduino was designed by (Kumar *et al.*, 2019) and implemented for domestic use that opens and closes the bin followed by a beep sound that allows the user to throw garbage into it.

A smart trash can that separates trash into biodegradable and non-biodegradable materials was created by (Mohanaprasadh *et al.*, 2022). The sensor identifies and separates the waste whenever a human approaches the trash can with waste in front of it (biodegradable or non-bio-degradable). When the trash can is full, a message will be sent to the person in charge instructing them to empty the trash can. Wet and dry garbage were automatically separated using a low-cost smart waste system, which was then dispatched for additional processing.

A Technology enabled smart waste collection and management system, using IOT was developed by Susila *et al.*, (2018), to screen the garbage container, the bin level was reported via sms to the respective authorities, in order to eliminate the overflow of the garbage. The bins utilized an Arduino UNO board, GSM and several sensors. Upon threshold detection, it is ensured that the stagnated waste in the bin is dispensed to help preserve environmental hygiene.

(Rahmayanti *et al.*, 2019) proposed a smart trash can, for implementing smart environment in a smart city, which can detect the type of waste that is discarded, and automatically place it in the right barrel. In order to achieve the dual goals of trash disposal in appropriate locations and trash minimization, an innovative technology for managing waste disposal through smart trash bins

and waste disposal trackers was devised by Karnalim *et al.*, (2020). The system offers smart bins and trash disposal trackers. In an attempt to address waste disposal issues, Slamet *et al.*, (2021) also suggested a block chain-based incentive system that includes a payment system for using wearable devices, Ethereum smart contracts, and smart trash bins.

A smart hand washing machine was designed and implemented using Arduino and presented by (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2021) at the 1st Multidisciplinary National Conference in Pharmaceutical Science and Technology, PHARMTECH 2021, Kano State Polytechnic, Kano state, the device used an ultrasonic sensor to detect the presence of hands and start the hand-washing cycle on its own. To compel users to use soap, it first pushed out the soap solution, followed by clean water. Room, (2019) also designed a hand-washing machine that prevents contact with any of its parts to prevent further transfer of COVID-19 and other related diseases from infected to uninfected persons with a device being shared in public places. Oo *et al.*, (2019), designed and modelled an automatic hand washing system, using a proximity sensing circuit and a DC motor, for washing of hands in various restaurants, in order to prevent the spread of bacteria and germs. Research has made it possible for an automatic hand washing system that conveniently involves three steps of hand washing practice; rinsing, soaping and drying to be implemented without any single contact from the user.

Furthermore, despite all these chains of advancement in the waste management, there is still the need for modifications in line with the current national and international situation, ranging from health challenges as experienced during the era of COVID-19 pandemic, requiring zero contact. The latter designs were able to proffer a sustainable solution to contactless waste disposal but failed in the aspect of segregation for proper recycling. Though the most recent automated waste segregator was able to tackle this issue but is still quite deficient in the area of ensuring recycling

by the designated waste management authority, as any individual can readily access the container of the segregated waste and cause litter after secondary use. But by means of a locked disposal unit, it is then ensured that the compartments containing waste are only accessed by the waste management authority. In addition to segregation, the need for adequate healthy living necessitates that after the waste disposal, the individuals ought to wash their hands and thus the provision of such integrated mechanisms as automated hand washer needs to be implemented as well for increased sustainable solution implementation.

In summary most research and studies in literature have not successfully integrated a contactless hand washer to the developed smart bin. However, in this COVID-19 era it has become imperative to proffer a solution which reduces human contact with waste and debris and therefore limits the spread of the virus. This research therefore proposes to fill this knowledge gap by proffering a solution, that improves, enhances and modifies the already existing systems, with a view to making it more effective, thus bringing about a smarter, cleaner, hands-free and contagion free environment, which will in turn benefit our institution, the society and the world at large.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Material Selection

In engineering several materials are available for application and selection depending on the designer's choice. The choice of a material for a given application can determine, to a large extent, the ultimate success or failure of the system, as it is the final practical decision in the design process. The choice of every single material in a design cannot be made independent of the choice of the process by which the material is to be formed, jointed, finished, and otherwise treated. However, cost must be considered, both in the choice of material and in the way the material is processed. Thus, for the purpose of this research, the following material considerations were set aside to guide the choice of the material selection, they are:

1. Cost
2. Availability
3. Durability
4. Manufacturability

After critical process consideration, and material selection choices based on the intended application, some materials met the material selection criteria, they include the following:

- a. Arduino UNO Microcontroller
- b. HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor
- c. SG-90 Servo Motor
- d. Lithium-ion battery-built power bank
- e. 40-Pin Rainbow Wire

- f. GSM Modem
- g. Mild steel – 45 x 45 x 5mm
- h. Mild steel sheet
- i. Water dispensing plastic container

3.1.1 Material Description

The Arduino UNO Microcontroller

The Arduino Uno is an open-source microcontroller board based on the Microchip ATmega328P microcontroller and developed by Arduino.cc and initially released in 2010. The board is equipped with sets of digital and analog input/output (I/O) pins, that may be interfaced to various expansion boards (shields) and other circuits. The board has 14 digital I/O pins (six capable of PWM output), 6 analog I/O pins, and is programmable with the Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment), via a type B USB cable. It can be powered by the USB cable or by an external 9-volt battery, though it accepts voltages between 7 and 20 volts. It is similar to the Arduino Nano and Leonardo.

Fig 3.1. Arduino UNO Board. (*Henry, 2022*)

Arduino UNO Power Overview

- i. External power supply voltage: 7V to 12V DC
- ii. USB power or externally via barrel jack connector

Table 3.1: Arduino UNO R3 Pins

Pin	Function
Vin	Voltage from external power jack
5V	5V output from on-board Voltage regulator chip
3.3V	3.3V output from on-board Voltage regulator chip
GND	3 pins for ground
IOREF	Tied to 5V, tells Arduino shields voltage level from which Arduino board operates
Reset	From RESET pin on MCU, tied to VCC through 10K resistor, pull to GND to reset

Arduino UNO Digital Input/ Output Overview

- i. It has 14 Digital Inputs and Outputs.
- ii. It has a logic level of 5V.
- iii. Its Sink/Source is 20mA per pin.
- iv. It utilizes Universal Asynchronous Serial Receiver/Transmitter (UART) for which pin 0 is for receiving and pin 1 is for transmitting.
- v. It has 8-bit PWM.
- vi. It has a Serial Peripheral Interface.

Arduino UNO Analog Inputs Overview

- i. Analog Input pins are A0, A1, A2, A3, A4, A5.
- ii. Its sampled input is from 0V to 5V and it has a 10 bits resolution.
- iii. The AREF pin can be used to adjust the upper limit of the input range.
- iv. It has Two-wire Interface COM.
- v. Pin A4 is SDA pin for data.
- vi. Pin A5 is SCL pin for clock.

Arduino UNO R3 Communications Overview

- i. It can communicate with a computer, another Arduino, shields, sensors.
- ii. Asynchronous communication (No clock).
- iii. UART TTL (5V)
 - a. On board ATmegaU16 programmed to function as USB to serial chip

- b. ATmegaU16 uses standard USB COM drivers so that no external drivers are required for communication with the board
- iv. Synchronous communication (Clock) uses SPI Pins 10, 11, 12, 13, and TWI pins A4 and A5.

Arduino Programming Overview

- i. The bootloader firmware comes already preinstalled with the Arduino UNO
- ii. New sketches can be uploaded via the USB
- iii. External programmer can upload sketches via the In-circuit serial programmer pins (ICSP)
- iv. It has 32 KB of Flash memory where the sketches are stored
- v. It possesses 2 KB of SRAM, which temporarily stores variables until the power supply is interrupted
- vi. It has 1 KB of EEPROM which stores long term information.

HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor

The word 'ultra' means 'beyond' and sonic means 'sound'. Combining the two of them together ultrasonic is a sound which is above the human hearing range (20 KHz).

An Ultrasonic sensor is a sensor that can detect ultrasound waves and convert the waves into electric signals or vice versa. An ultrasonic sensor is capable of measuring the total distance between itself and an object by sending out a wave at a certain frequency and listening for that wave to bounce back to it. During this, it records the time taken between when the wave was generated and when it bounced back in order to calculate the distance between it and an object.

Fig 3.2. Diagram showing the basic operation of the HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor. (Dejan, 2022)

HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor Features

- i. It has a 5V DC power supply
- ii. Its Quiescent current is less than 2 mA
- iii. Its working current is 15 mA
- iv. Its effectual angle is less than 15 degrees
- v. Its ranging distance is between 2 cm – 400 cm/1” – 13 ft
- vi. Its Resolution is 0.3 cm
- vii. Its measuring angle is 30 degrees
- viii. Its Trigger pulse width is 10 μ S
- ix. Its dimension is 45 mm x 20 mm x 15 mm

HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor Pin Configuration

The HC-SR04 is an ultrasonic sensor, also known as an ultrasonic transducer that is based on a transmitter and receiver and mainly used to determine the distance from the target object. The amount of time it takes to send and receive waves will determine how far the object is placed from the sensor. It mainly depends on the sound waves working on “non-contact” technology. The required distance of the target object is measured without any damage, giving accurate and precise details. This sensor comes with a range between 2 cm to 400 cm and is used in a

wide range of applications including speed and direction measurement, wireless charging, humidifiers, medical ultrasonography, sonar, burglar alarms, and non-destructive testing.

Fig 3.3: HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor Pins. (Aqeel, 2018)

Table 3.2: HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor Pins

Pin Number	Pin Name	Description
1	VCC	The is used to power the sensor with 5V
2	Trigger	This is an Input pin which has to be kept high for 10 μ s to initialize measurement by sending Ultrasound wave.
3	Echo	This is an output pin which goes high for a period of time equal to the time taken for the Ultrasound wave to return back to the sensor.
4	Ground	This pin is connected to the ground of the system

Working of Principle HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor

Sonar is used by the ultrasonic sensor to obtain the distance between itself and an object. Here’s how it works:

- a. The trig pin(transmitter) sends a signal which is a high-frequency sound
- b. The signal is reflected once it hits an object
- c. The echo pin(receiver) receives the reflection

For example, if the distance between the object and the sensor is 10 cm, and the speed of sound is 340 m/s, the sound wave will need to travel about 294 μ s. The value gotten at the echo pin will be twice that number because the wave travels to and fro. To get the distance in cm, the time gotten at the echo pin is multiplied by 0.034 and divided by 2.

Applications of HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor

- a. It is used in robots to detect and avoid obstacles in the path of the robot.
- b. It is used to measure distance within a wide range (200 cm - 400 cm)
- c. It can be used for mapping of objects around a sensor by rotation of sensor.
- d. Since the ultrasonic waves are capable of penetrating water, it can be used to measure depths in places like pits, wells, etc.

SG-90 Servo Motor

A servo motor is an electrical device that pushes or rotates objects with high precision. If there is need for an object to be rotated at a specific angle or distance, then a servo motor is used. A servo motor consists of a motor that uses a servo mechanism. The two types of servo motors are the DC servo motors (DC powered) and the AC servo motor (AC powered) where the difference between them is the input power. A very high torque can be obtained from a small and lightweight servo motor which allows these servo motors to be used in applications like robots, toy cars, etc. The main reason why a servo motor is used is because of its high angle precision, i.e. after rotating, it will stop and wait for the next instruction to happen, unlike a normal electric motor which rotates as long as it is

being supplied power and stops rotating when power supply is turned off.

Fig 3.6. SG-90 Servo Motor. (*Servo Motor SG-90, n.d.*)

Lithium-Ion Battery-Built Power Bank

A lithium-ion battery (20000 mAh) power bank is a type of rechargeable battery composed of cells in which lithium ions move from the negative electrode through an electrolyte to the positive electrode during discharge and back when charging. Li-ion cells use an intercalated lithium compound as the material at the positive electrode and typically graphite at the negative electrode. Li-ion batteries have a high energy density, no memory effect (other than LFP cells) and low self-discharge. Cells can be manufactured to prioritize either energy or power density. They can however be a safety hazard since they contain flammable electrolytes and if damaged or incorrectly charged can lead to explosions and fires.

Figure 3.9: Lithium-Ion Battery Built Power Bank

40-Pin Rainbow Wire

This rainbow wire provides a convenient way to connect the signal in our project. We could always pull the rainbow wires off to make individual jumpers or keep them together to make neatly organized wire harnesses. The color-coding was used to organize power, ground and other signal types to keep the circuit organized. The length was 20 cm.

Fig 3.10. The jumper wires. Sourced from (HUB360, 2022)

GSM Modem

A GSM modem is a specialized type of wireless modem that works with a GSM wireless network.

It accepts a SIM card, and operates over a subscription to a mobile operator, just like a mobile phone. GSM Modem sends and receives data through radio waves in our experiment we used GSM 900 A (Figure 3.11).

Figure 3.11: GSM modem. (*In-Depth*, 2018)

LCD display

A liquid-crystal display (LCD) is a flat-panel display or other electronically modulated optical device that uses the light-modulating properties of liquid crystals. Liquid crystals do not emit light directly, instead a backlight or reflector is used to produce images in colour or monochrome. LCDs are available to display arbitrary images (as in a general-purpose computer display) or fixed images with low information content, which can be displayed or hidden, such as pre-set words, digits, and 7-segment displays, as in a digital clock. They use the same basic technology, except that arbitrary images are made up of a large number of small pixels, while other displays have larger elements (Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12: LCD display. Sourced from (Electropeak, 2021)

Water dispensing plastic container

This serves as a water container and water reservoir for the hand washer. It was attached as a sub unit device, to the main structure (the waste bin).

Frame

The frame structure in any material is one that is made stable by a skeleton that is able to stand by itself as a rigid structure without depending on floors or walls to resist deformation. Thus, materials such as wood, steel, and reinforced concrete, which are strong in both tension and compression, make the best members for framing.

Factors Considered before the Selection of the Material for the Frame

The following are the factors that should be considered before selecting materials for the Frame:

1. Ease of machining
2. Cost
3. Availability

4. Resistance to corrosion
5. Resistance to deformation

For the framing structure, mild steel – 45 x 5 mm was selected because of its unique characteristics like machinability, weldability, affordability and resistance to corrosion.

Description of Mild Steel (Angular Profile)

Mild steel angular profile is an L-shaped cross-section used in the construction of buildings and structures. The most commonly cast off mild steel angular profile are the ones forming a 90-degree angle with two sides of equal length and width. The angles with uniform sides are called equal angles and the ones with one side bigger than the other are called unequal angles. Equal and unequal angles are highly versatile in application and can be used in several engineering applications such as reinforcement, transmission towers, bridges, sheds, etc.

Fig 3.14.: Frame of the System

3.2 Description of Equipment Used

Table 3.9: Equipment descriptions

Equipment Used	Description
Soldering Iron	A soldering iron is a hand tool used in soldering. It supplies heat to melt a lead solder so that it can flow into the joint between two work pieces.
Electrical Tape (Black)	Electrical tape is a type of pressure sensitive tape used to insulate electrical wires and other materials that conduct electricity.
Screw Drivers	This is a tool, manual or powered, used for screwing and unscrewing screws.
Multimeter	A Multimeter is an electronic measuring instrument that combines several measurement functions in one unit. Used in measuring voltage, current and resistance.

3.2 Description of Softwares used

3.3.1 Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment) Software

The program code written for Arduino is known as a sketch. The software used for developing such sketches for an Arduino is commonly known as the Arduino IDE. The Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) is a cross-platform application (for Windows, macOS, and Linux) that is written in the Java programming language. It originated from the IDE for the languages Processing and Wiring. It includes a code editor with features such as text cutting and pasting, searching and replacing text, automatic indenting, brace matching, and syntax highlighting, and provides simple one-click mechanisms to compile and upload programs to an Arduino board. It also contains a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions and a hierarchy of operation menus. The Arduino IDE supports the languages C and C++ using special rules of code structuring. The Arduino IDE supplies a software library from the Wiring project, which provides many common input and output procedures. User-written code only requires two basic functions, for starting the sketch and the main program loop,

that are compiled and linked with a program stub `main()` into an executable cyclic executive program with the GNU tool chain, also included with the IDE distribution. The Arduino In the IDE, the AVRDUDE program is utilized to transform the executable code into a hexadecimal-encoded text file. This file is then loaded into the Arduino board through a loader program present in the board's firmware. This IDE contains the following parts in it:

1. **Text editor:** This is where the simplified code can be written using a simplified version of C++ programming language.
2. **Message area:** It displays error and also gives a feedback on saving and exporting the code.
3. **Text:** The console displays text output by the Arduino environment including complete error messages and other information.
4. **Console Toolbar:** This toolbar contains various buttons like Verify, Upload, New, Open, Save and Serial Monitor. On the bottom right hand corner of the window, the Development Board and the Serial Port in use is displayed.

Fig 3.15: Arduino IDE

Table 3.3: Description of the Softwares used.

Software Used	Description
SolidWorks	A solid modelling computer-aided design and computer-aided engineering computer program that runs primarily on Microsoft windows.
Arduino IDE	An open-source software that makes it easy to write code and upload it to the board.

3.4 Methods Applied

Three different methods were applied according to the order shown in the flowchart on Fig. 3.16

Fig 3.16: Project Flowchart

3.4.1 System design

The block diagram of the system was designed as shown in the flowcharts on Fig. 3.17.

Fig 3.17: System design Flowchart

3.4.2 CAD Model

SOLIDWORKS was utilized for the CAD drafting and analysis because of its extraordinary capability in the field of design and analysis of engineering products. The compact design accelerators and comprehensive finite element analysis capability makes it an ideal tool for use in developing machines and its components.

Fig 3.18: CAD Model of the system

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Experimental Setup

The outcome of this project is an Arduino-Controlled Real Time Waste Monitoring System which detects presence of objects, opens the lid, and closes it after the specified delay time. The sensors monitor the waste compartment level and sends a feedback SMS to the authority in charge, when the bin is getting full, for proper disposal of the waste. An indicator Light (Red and Green) signifies the bin-full and bin-empty states respectively, with an LCD display showing the bin status at any given time. The attached automatic hand washer works efficient and disposes water without contact in order to achieve the desired output.

4.2 Simulation Codes Development

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
```

```
#include <LiquidCrystal_I2C.h>
```

```
String message=(" AUTOMATIC WASTE BIN: Dispose Waste, Wash Your Hand & Keep FUO  
CLEAN! ");
```

```
int length;
```

```
LiquidCrystal_I2C lcd(0x27,20,4);
```

```
char array1[] = "AUTOMATIC WASTE BIN";
```

```
char array2[] = "M: Empty";
```

```
char array3[] = "M:H-Full";
```

```
char array4[] = "M: Full";
```

```
char array5[] = "N-M: Empty";  
char array6[] = "N-M:H-Full";  
char array7[] = "N-M: Full";  
char array8[] = "Water Available";  
char array9[] = "Water Not Available";
```

```
//Bin Compartment 1
```

```
int Red = 14, Green = 15, Blue = 16;  
int trigPin1 = 12; // 1  
int echoPin1 = 13;
```

```
//Bin Compartment 2
```

```
int Red2 = 7, Green2 = 6, Blue2 = 5;  
int trigPin2 = 10;  
int echoPin2 = 11;
```

```
//Water level checker
```

```
int Red3 = 2, Green3 = 17, Blue3;  
int trigPin3 = 8;  
int echoPin3 = 9;;  
int t = 1000;
```

```
//Sim 900L
```

```
SoftwareSerial mySerial(4,3); // RX, TX
```

```
void setup() {
```

```
  pinMode(trigPin1, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(echoPin1, INPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(trigPin2, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(echoPin2, INPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(trigPin3, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(echoPin3, INPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Red, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Green, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Blue, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Red2, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Green2, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Blue2, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Red3, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode (Green3, OUTPUT);
```

```

pinMode (Blue3, OUTPUT);

lcd.init();

lcd.backlight();

Serial.begin (9600);

mySerial.begin(9600);

length=message.length();
}

void firstsensor(){ // This function is for first sensor.

int duration1, distance1;

digitalWrite (trigPin1, HIGH);digitalWrite (trigPin1, LOW);

duration1 = pulseIn (echoPin1, HIGH);distance1 = (duration1/2) / 29.1;

Serial.print("1st Sensor: ");Serial.print(distance1);Serial.println("cm");

delay(t/5);

if (distance1 >= 25){

digitalWrite(Green,HIGH);digitalWrite(Red,LOW);digitalWrite(Blue,LOW);

Serial.println("OK.. not full ");

lcd.setCursor(0,2);

lcd.print(array2);}

else if (distance1>=10 && distance1<25){

```

```

digitalWrite(Green,LOW);digitalWrite(Red,LOW);digitalWrite(Blue,HIGH);

Serial.println("Half Full ");

lcd.setCursor(0,2);

lcd.print(array3);

}

else{

    digitalWrite(Green,LOW);digitalWrite(Red,HIGH);digitalWrite(Blue,LOW); // code for
send SMS

    mySerial.println("AT+CMGF=1"); //Sets the GSM Module in Text Mode

    delay(t/2);mySerial.println("AT+CMGS=\"+09036023522\"\\r"); //your mobile number

    delay(t/2);

    mySerial.println("Bin1 Full (Metal comp), Disposal required! ");

    delay(t/2);

    mySerial.println((char)26);// ASCII code of CTRL+Z

    delay(t);

    Serial.println("Full ");

    lcd.setCursor(0,2);

    lcd.print(array4);

    }}

void secondsensor(){// This function is for second sensor.

    int duration2, distance2;

    digitalWrite (trigPin2, HIGH);

```

```

digitalWrite (trigPin2, LOW);

duration2 = pulseIn (echoPin2, HIGH);

distance2 = (duration2/2) / 29.1;

Serial.print("2nd Sensor: ");Serial.print(distance2);Serial.println("cm");

delay(t);

if (distance2 >= 25){

    digitalWrite(Green2,HIGH);digitalWrite(Red2,LOW);digitalWrite(Blue2,LOW);

    Serial.println("OK.. not full ");

    lcd.setCursor(9,2);

    lcd.print(array5);}

else if (distance2>=10 && distance2<25){

    digitalWrite(Green2,LOW);digitalWrite(Red2,LOW);digitalWrite(Blue2,HIGH);

    Serial.println("Half Full ");

    lcd.setCursor(9,2);

    lcd.print(array6);

    }

//if (distance1<=10) {

else{

    digitalWrite(Green2,LOW);digitalWrite(Red2,HIGH);digitalWrite(Blue2,LOW); // code for
send SMS

    mySerial.println("AT+CMGF=1"); //Sets the GSM Module in Text Mode

    delay(t/2);mySerial.println("AT+CMGS=\"+09036023522\"\\r"); //your mobile number

```

```

delay(t/2);

mySerial.println("Bin2 Full (Non Metal comp), Disposal required! ");

delay(t/2);

mySerial.println((char)26);// ASCII code of CTRL+Z

delay(t);

Serial.println("Full "); lcd.setCursor(9,2);

lcd.print(array7);

}}

void thirdsensor(){ // This function is for third sensor.

int duration3, distance3;

digitalWrite (trigPin3, HIGH);

digitalWrite (trigPin3, LOW);

duration3 = pulseIn (echoPin3, HIGH);

distance3 = (duration3/2) / 29.1;

Serial.print("3rd Sensor: ");Serial.print(distance3);Serial.println("cm");

delay(t);

if (distance3 <= 12){

digitalWrite(Green3,HIGH);digitalWrite(Red3,LOW);digitalWrite(Blue3,LOW);

Serial.println("OK.. Water available");

lcd.setCursor(0,3);

lcd.print(array8);}

//else if (distance3>=10 && distance3<25){

//digitalWrite(Green3,LOW);digitalWrite(Red3,LOW);digitalWrite(Blue3,HIGH);

```

```

    //Serial.println("Half Full ");

else{

    digitalWrite(Green3,LOW);digitalWrite(Red3,HIGH);digitalWrite(Blue3,LOW); // code for
send SMS

    mySerial.println("AT+CMGF=1"); //Sets the GSM Module in Text Mode

    delay(t/2);mySerial.println("AT+CMGS=\"+09036023522\"\\r"); //your mobile number

    delay(t/2);

    mySerial.println("Water low, refill Required! ");

    delay(t/2);

    mySerial.println((char)26);// ASCII code of CTRL+Z

    delay(t);

    Serial.println("Water low, refill Required!");

    lcd.setCursor(0,3);

    lcd.print(array9);

    }}

void loop(){

    Serial.println("\\n");

    firstsensor();

    secondsensor();

    thirdsensor();

    lcd.setCursor(0,1);

```

```
lcd.print(array1);  
}  
  
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>  
  
#include <Servo.h>  
  
Servo servo;  
  
int inductive = 4;  
int pump = 7;  
  
//Lid OPENER  
int trigPin = 3;  
int echoPin = 2;  
  
//WASTE SEGREGATOR  
int motorpin1 = 7;  
int motorpin2 = 8;  
  
//WATER DISPENSER  
int trigPin2 = 5;
```

```
int echoPin2 = 6;

void setup() {
  servo.attach(9);
  Serial.begin (9600);

  pinMode(trigPin, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(echoPin, INPUT);

  pinMode(trigPin2, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(echoPin2, INPUT);

  pinMode(inductive, INPUT);
  pinMode(pump, OUTPUT);
}

void firstsensor(){
  long duration, distance;
  digitalWrite(trigPin, LOW);
  delayMicroseconds(2);
  digitalWrite(trigPin, HIGH);
  delayMicroseconds(10);
```

```
digitalWrite(trigPin, LOW);  
duration = pulseIn(echoPin, HIGH);  
distance = (duration/2) / 29.1;  
if (distance <= 35) {  
  
Serial.println("the distance is less than 10");  
servo.write(120);  
delay(1500);  
  
}  
  
else {  
  
servo.write(0);  
  
}  
  
if (distance > 60 || distance <= 0){  
  
Serial.println("The distance is more than 60");  
  
}  
  
else {  
  
Serial.print(distance);  
Serial.println(" cm");  
  
}  
  
delay(10);  
  
}
```

```
void secondsensor(){// This function is for second sensor.
```

```
    if (inductive == HIGH) {  
        digitalWrite (motorpin1, HIGH);  
        delay(20);  
        digitalWrite (motorpin1, LOW);  
        delay(20);
```

```
        digitalWrite (motorpin2, HIGH);  
        delay (20);  
        digitalWrite (motorpin1, LOW);
```

```
    }
```

```
}
```

```
void thirdsensor(){ // This function is for third sensor.
```

```
    int duration2, distance2;  
    digitalWrite (trigPin2, HIGH);  
    delayMicroseconds (10);  
    digitalWrite (trigPin2, LOW);  
    duration2 = pulseIn (echoPin2, HIGH);  
    distance2 = (duration2/2) / 29.1;
```

```
    Serial.print("2nd Sensor: ");
```

```
Serial.print(distance2);  
  
Serial.print("cm");  
  
if (distance2<=15){  
    digitalWrite(pump,HIGH);  
}  
  
else{  
  
    digitalWrite(pump,LOW);}  
  
}
```

```
void loop(){  
Serial.println("\n");  
firstsensor ();  
secondsensor();  
  
thirdsensor();  
  
//delay(100);  
  
}
```

4.3 Results and Discussions

The various tests carried out on the final hardware revealed the limitations of the detection algorithm. The limitations were related to cases of some obstacles not being detected, and this was as a result of the sensor not being able to measure objects outside the measuring range, of the sensor and at the same time not being able to differentiate between the presence, or absence of objects passing in front of it. To avoid this, the testing was further carried out in an enclosed area where the wall was the only obstacle and the system worked perfectly. To implement this system, more sensors have to be used in order to cover a wider range for object detection. However, the sensor used is one of the most important components. It is a very important component because the performance of this robot is critically dependent on the accuracy of the sensor. The HC-SR04 has a measuring range of 30 degrees and 300 cm. It operates by emitting a high-frequency sound wave (40 KHz) through one of its piezo-electric transducers and detects the returning pulses (echo) through another transducer. When objects were not within the specified range, the sound waves emitted by the sensor will not hit any objects and therefore, not effectively detect any object. This was an issue because the sensor does not sense objects which do not fall within the sensor range. Aside from this range issue, the sensor was able to detect objects within its range.

Furthermore, there was a lot of stress on the battery coming from the components, especially the motors. The motors need a lot of energy for their operation, especially cheaper motors because they have less efficiency. The power demand needed to operate the system to a very high efficiency needs three lithium ion batteries of 3.5 volts each, to be connected in series. The maximum voltage to be supplied to an Arduino board is 12V and the minimum is 5V. Power is being looped from the power bank to the Arduino board. When the power source is not enough

or more power than required are used, it becomes unsatisfactory to the power demand of the system, as some of the components barely respond to the programming. The batteries need to be increased in series not exceeding the rated voltage value in order to relieve the stress from the batteries.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The Arduino Uno based AUTOMATIC SENSITIVE WASTE BIN WITH AN INTEGRATED CONTACTLESS HANDWASHER SYSTEM (ASWCHW-001) was developed for smart waste monitoring in real time using the SIM card module. The system developed here uses an interface created by an Arduino microcontroller programmed chip, to work with different components including sensors such as ultrasonic sensors, actuators comprising electric motors, and a water dispensing system. All enclosed in a protective metal casing, shielded from environmental degradation factors, including corrosion which was prevented by painting the surfaces and other necessary treatment processes. The system was able to efficiently handle waste disposal, and its design was found effective for the proper waste disposal in the premises of the university environment. This was very helpful in maintaining a clean and conducive academic environment free from breeding dangerous microorganisms and transmission of diseases. Thus, the system comes in handy as an efficient and appreciable solution in the modern day waste management and technologically adapted innovation.

5.2 Recommendations

In the course of this research certain observations were made, and based on these observations the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Future enhancement of this waste management system can be done by connecting this system to the cloud server, for increased of feedback rage and alert messages response, when the dustbin gets full.

2. Since the waste management system contains electrical wires, which must be adequately protected to prevent short circuiting when liquid waste is disposed into the dustbin waterproof connection such as the use of silicon tapes, is highly recommended.
3. Also future work can be done by using liquid detecting sensors, for efficient liquid waste disposal into the dustbin.
4. The water dispensing unit needs to be well properly channeled and an ethanol base disinfectant solution added to effectively kill germs and reduce disease transmission.

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Appendixes

Plate 1: Complete Project Work

Plate 2: The Water Can Under construction

Plate 3: Body Fabrication front view

Plate 4: Body Fabrication Back View